

COMANDANTE CHÁVEZ: A ŽIŽEKIAN ENCOUNTER WITH THE REAL

di Jesús H. Ramírez

Abstract

This paper is about Slavoj Žižek's analysis of Hugo Chávez and how, from my point of view, his relating to his constituents (the people) can be viewed as a manifestation of Žižek's take on how one interpassively encounters the Real. I use Chávez as a figure head of controversial leadership. All at once, such figures are loved, hated, unsupported, and supported by many. However, I think his case is particularly interesting because in this present moment we are constantly bombarded by the Lacanian triad of the Symbolic, Imaginary, and Real as it pertains current leadership. With the current war in Ukraine and the persistent topic of misinformation versus authentic information, it is crucial to examine our narratives about our leaders so that we can gain an understanding of our form of participation. In examining Hugo Chávez, we have enough distance from his reign to examine the role of interpassivity. From this, we can extrapolate how interpassivity plays a role in our way of relating to the Zelenskys, Putins, Bidens, and Trumps of the world. Through this interpassive lens, we can identify how their being our symbolic representations remains a necessary condition for our desire for change in a world that frequently shows us how disempowered we are when our leaders act.

Keywords: Reality, Zizek, Chavez, Interpassivity

There is an illness, I heard, when the heart – as an organ – simply grows too big and cannot function properly, unable to pump all the blood through its widened veins. Maybe Chávez really died of having too big a heart¹ (Slavoj Žižek)

Hugo Chávez died from cancer on March 5th, 2013. Afterward, a presidential election was held in Venezuela. Nicolás Maduro, Chávez' former vice-president, won. Immediately after, protests ensued, calling for a recount and the organizing of more mass protests in Caracas, using the old form of *cacerolazos*: marching while banging on pots and pans. Maduro publicly argued against this march, saying: «I am saving them from themselves»². This is the continued legacy of Hugo Chávez, a man who openly supported the people of Venezuela, yet who also could not seem to control an economy that was supposed to be autonomously run by its citizens. Ultimately, the power and efficacy of Chávez' leadership was based on a separation between the citizens and their country, where Chávez' brand of symbolic *Bolivarismo* became the gap between the people and country. He would be of the people and for the people even though his way of governing did not produce much *for* the people. Chávez inspired Venezuelans to save themselves from themselves by having him as the placeholder, symbolically performing as the embodiment of the people's will, the Chávez symbol that would allow critics and supporters to pour their desires into. Chávez would become the interpassive vessel for all.

¹ S. ŽIŽEK, *A Heart Larger Than Life* (Blog da Boitempo, 2013) <http://blog-daboitempo.com.br/2013/03/11/a-heart-larger-than-life/blog> (accessed on 4/20/13).

² R. CARROLL, *Hugo Chávez: Poor Boy from the Plains Who Became Leftwing Figurehead* (The Guardian, 2013); cfr. website <http://www.guardian.co.uk/world/2013/mar/05/hugo-Chavez-poor-leftwing-figurehead> (accessed April 10, 2013).

In Slavoj Žižek's post-Chávez analysis, Žižek described the leader's legacy as a manifestation of his "big heart". The symbol of Chávez serves the Žižekian concept of interpassivity, wherein Chavez's "big heart" for the people only showcased his separation from them, a separation that is best described as a Lacanian "Real". This paper will take Žižek's concept of interpassivity and apply it to Chávez's attempted implementation of Bolívarismo in Venezuela, where Bolívarismo evoked former president Simon Bolivar's idea of the people helping to lead their country toward freedom. I will argue that the view of Chávez as being a symbol for Bolívarismo placed his detractors and supporters in an awkward interpassive position, making it difficult for these groups to confront Chávez as simply another imaginary symbol within the Real without having to confront their complicity in bringing him into power. I will conclude with an analysis of how Chávez was the only interactive player in the affairs of Venezuela and that he did so by letting everyone else use him as an interpassive way of encountering the Real, effectively becoming a scapegoat to all people, world leaders, masses, and intellectuals who either held him responsible for their hopes toward change or for their worries about the future of Venezuela.

Jacques Lacan said: «Man speaks, then, but it is because the symbol has made him man»³. Though Chávez spoke for the people, *Bolívarismo* made him for the people. The elements of *Bolívarismo* center on a person creating the conditions for life by aspiring toward freedom and enlightenment. In his writing in 1819 Angostura Address, Simón Bolívar, the General of the Venezuelan military who became President of Colombia, Peru, and then Bolivia, thoroughly laid the framework for what was later called *Bolívarismo*. This was a general concept of maintaining independence with the assistance of a governing body; it would also be an idea that would become a rallying cry for much of Latin America. To advocate this idea was tantamount to arguing for basic autonomy and freedom. However, a crucial aspect of this idea (lost within the

³ J. LACAN, *Écrits. A selection*, W.W. Norton & Company, New York - London 1977, p. 65.

mainstream media that has either vilified or praised Chávez) is that the government checks freedom. In his Angostura Address, Bolívar said:

From absolute freedom, nations always plunge into absolute power, and the mean between these two extremes is supreme social freedom. The pernicious idea of unlimited freedom is a product of abstract theories. Let us keep public power within the limits prescribed by reason and interest and conform our national will to the possibilities allowed by the fair distribution of power⁴.

For Bolívar, freedom was an instrument of humanity. It could be used perniciously or to our benefit, so long as it was kept in moderation and in proportion to the abilities of the individuals enacting it. In his comments regarding North America, freedom was misused properly. Initially, it was set up as a cornerstone of the U.S. Constitution, but it was left to the adjudication of a government that itself was free to issue laws against the fiscal interests of its citizens. Bolívar said of the United States that:

the Americans, within the Spanish system still in force, and perhaps now more than ever, occupy no other place in society than that of servants suited for work or, at best, that of simply consumers, and even this role is limited by appalling restrictions⁵.

Rather than subjecting Bolivians to such restrictions, he envisioned a country where people would understand the mechanisms of government that control them. His goal was to have a state that would align with the character and customs of the people. In short, *Bolívarismo* advocated checked freedom, education, and preservation of the dignity of the people. His draft of Bolivia's constitution even states that to be a citizen, a Bolivian must be able to read and write; in addition, a Bolivian

⁴ S. BOLÍVAR, *El Libertador: Writings of Simón Bolívar*, ed. and trans. by F. H. Fornoff, Oxford University Press, New York 2003, p. 47.

⁵ BOLÍVAR, *El Libertador*, cit., p. 19.

must fight for the security of the Republic even at the cost of their lives and property⁶. Thus, *Bolívarismo*, as outlined and practiced by Simón Bolívar, was designed for interaction guided by orders that would have citizens align their capacities within a governmental scale. It would not absolutely bind them to the government, but would allow them to navigate it toward the benefit of local populations that normally do not see themselves in power.

Such interaction would belie interpassivity, where this concept is marked by using a symbol as a substitute to express your desires. The type of interaction from *Bolívarismo* would be closer to Žizek's concept of *interpellation* where an interpellated individual is «the addressee of an ideological call»⁷. The people are called to act by *Bolívarismo* because activity is inherent to the concept. They must heed it to be considered authentic citizens. How this plays itself out is the essential subject of this paper as we see a movement from interpellation to interpassivity, wherein the people bypass their involvement by subbing in Chávez as a symbol.

According to Lacan, the symbolic is composed of rules regarding how an object operates in the world. Employed by Chávez, *Bolívarismo* became a symbolic way of being. He used this concept to connect with the people and to evoke traces of Bolívar. *Bolívarismo* has its own set of rules, but any person or collective can embody this code. Despite it originating in Bolívar, the concept survived his death to be symbolic. For any symbol to survive, it must be sustained by interpellation or with interpassivity. The former requires direct interaction, while the latter does not. Interpassivity occurs when the individual no longer acts but uses something or someone to act *for* it. For instance, a “like” on a social media post may sometimes mean more to a social media user than actual comments from people about how they enjoy the content. The number

⁶ Cfr. *Ibid.*, p. 65.

⁷ S. ŽIŽEK, *For They Know Not What They Do: Enjoyment as a Political Factor*, Verso, London - New York 2008, p. 108.

of “likes” and symbols of engagement, reflected in actual numbers (like a ticker), become the medium of enjoyment to the point where the user may not even express elation, but uses the high number as the expression of *their* elation. As such, the only thing exhibiting enjoyment is the high number, signified by a heart or thumbs up icon, depending on which application one uses. Concepts can use people as much as any other object or media platform can use people. *Bolivarismo* is a concept that appears to, through a Zizekian lens, enjoy its users. Though it is a special take on Bolívar’s understanding of the symbolic idea of the Enlightenment (rational public engagement with the government), *Bolivarismo* grew to mean something beyond its historical context, originally animated by people, it now animates the will of the people. Interpassively, it awaits the people to animate it through their belief that they are somehow influencing the government.

Bolivarismo would not hold as a concept that is “for the people” without Bolívar’s insistence that the revolutionary spirit and participation of the people and this aspect provided a crucial alteration to the principles of Enlightenment, which were in vogue in Bolívar’s time. In general, the key element of Latin American Philosophy, for which Bolívar is considered a theoretical root, is that the collective experience of the people is paramount. The root of life would be found in the circumstances of the community of individuals within Latin America. This is a crucial difference from the Enlightenment, which held that universal principles were supreme over one’s irrational whims, desires, and even religious commitments. With Christianity being influential for Latin American reality, *Bolivarismo* represented a modification of Enlightenment and fidelity to religion. Seen as a monumental and historical figure in Latin America, Bolívar intellectualized the problematic of colonialism in Latin America and asserted a people-driven approach to government that historically affected communities to the point where the symbol of *Bolivarismo* was abstracted from the man himself, making him an imaginary of a symbolic order that he created. This would also happen

to Hugo Chávez when he took up the symbolic order of *Bolívarismo* and changed it to *Chávismo*.

The imaginary is taken as the image of a thing, whether in linguistic form or an actual shape. It is the instantiation of the symbol. The symbolic meaning remains, but the imaginary can look different. As an imaginary, Chávez became *Bolívarismo* by coming into public consciousness through revolutionary acts. Chávez's first forays into the public mainstream in 1992, when he led a failed coup against the president of Venezuela, embodied *Bolívarismo*. His failure turned into a symbol of the people against the oppressive government, but in Lacanian terms, Chávez himself became the new imaginary of *Bolívarismo*. Within the imaginary, he became a symbol of his commitment to the rights of Venezuelan people. Yet, while becoming a positive symbol to Venezuelans, he also become a negative symbol of socialism to the United States.

Chávez's divisive presence within the imaginary was so only because of perception. In one way, he is a socialist martyr and in another he is a socialist tyrant. As a socialist martyr he is *Bolívarismo* incarnate; a person that came from the slums of Venezuela. However, as a socialist tyrant, he is a totalitarian, and this is connected to his political decisions in Venezuela. For Žižek, this is problematic (despite his benevolent eulogy of Chávez). In *Did Somebody Say Totalitarianism?* Žižek discusses this problem, seeing the imaginary and symbolic as a relationship connected by belief. He says: «This very problematic of belief, the fact that the need to believe is consubstantial with human subjectivity, is what makes the standard argument evoked by believers in order to disarm their opponents problematic»⁸. For some, Chávez could never be a tyrant, but this perspective generated from the need for him to be a placeholder, the interpassive object of their belief. He is supposed to be the expression of a revolutionary spirit that helps those in need and cannot be anything less because if the interpassive object is less then, the individual believer becomes less. As such, he is simultaneously viewed as the heir apparent

⁸ ID., *Did Somebody Say Totalitarianism?*, Verso, London - New York 2001, p. 89.

to Bolívar's legacy to those who need this belief and as a totalitarian that destroyed his country's economy through socialism to those who need him to be that tyrant.

Žižek, looking for the psychological mechanism, turns from belief to shared guilt, saying: «If there is a 'psychological' mechanism at work in late Socialist ideology, it is therefore not that of belief but, rather, that of *shared guilt*»⁹. *Shared guilt* is the collective shame of violating one's standards. However, given the connection between the Lacanian triad and shared guilt, belief still has a significant role. It is precisely because Chávez was the imaginary for *Bolívarismo* that the role of belief is necessary; it makes sense of shared guilt. It is empirically clear that Chávez was not Bolívar; however, Chávez was taken to be representative of that concept, even though many Venezuelans remained jobless and poor due to state control that depended on oil to sustain the economy. If he is not *Bolívarismo* (or even *Chavismo*) then Venezuelans do not have interpassivity which is what remains of any aspirations toward interaction between citizens and government in the spirit of Bolívar. All the while, in the Lacanian Real, if a problem arose then Chávez's solution was money, which came from the global market value of their oil resources¹⁰. «If the basic petrostate trick is turn control of the state's oil dollars into control of the state, Chávez has merely brought the system up to date, yielding a petrostate for the 21st century»¹¹. By petrostate, the authors mean a state that is solely dependent on its oil resources.

While Chávez was seen as the new Bolívar and as he also had his constituents involved in the community organizing of their municipalities, they had to reflect on their support for Chávez: to support this imaginary as a symbol or to not support for him being the imaginary that is constituted by the Real. In other words, the question was between the ideal perception of him and the non-ideal, which was the Real. Judging

⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 90.

¹⁰ Cfr. F. TORO, J.C. NAGEL, *Blogging the Revolution: Caracas Chronicles and the Hugo Chávez Era*, Cognitio Books, Hexham (UK) 2013, p. 500.

¹¹ *Ibid.*, p. 529.

by his popularity and his continuous victories in re-election, the choice was made to consider him as the symbol. Interpassivity remained. However, to hold this requires a committed belief, and this is what leads to a collective guilt, wherein Venezuelans were knowledgeable about their destitute situation and thus knowledgeable that Chávez was not making prudent economic decisions to alleviate it. Yet, support for him remained. This also means that the interpretation of shared guilt, existing in reference to Chávez as the imaginary, hinges on a belief about Chávez as construed by a particular kind of revolutionary symbol that merely speaks on behalf of the poor.

Fleshing out what Žižek interpassivity postpones the Real, we can see that the Real would be the area of the “Impossible”, where the imaginary plays itself out all while the symbolic rules it. Lacan saw the Real as representing “fraud”, “absence”, and the “impossible” because of the discrepancy between the ideality of the symbolic and how it plays in the imaginary. The fraud reveals itself for what it is: We think we are playing out the imaginary according to the symbolic order of things, but we are being played by it. We are closer to the fraudulent process of it all than we are to that which we desired to enact in the first place. Consequently, the symbol represents absence, what is not there. The Real is the impossible because the meeting of the symbolic and imaginary cannot fully capture the problematic of the Real. Instead, the Real showcases absence and fraud, our deficiencies in properly encountering it. Žižekian interpassivity informs us that though we aim to do things one way, we accomplish a revelation of something else. He writes in *Organs Without Bodies*: «It is only within this distance that subjectivization proper can take place: what makes me a ‘human subject’ is the very fact that I cannot be reduced to my symbolic identity, that I display a wealth of idiosyncratic features»¹². Though fraudulent, we are revealed in what we are not in an objective sense: We are not the symbol. What we project to *be*, the symbol cannot *be*. We are human beings trying to be something we cannot be.

¹² S. ŽIŽEK, *Organs without Bodies*, Routledge, New York 2012, p. 159.

The Real is the «entire complex set of contingent set of circumstances»¹³. In the case of Venezuela and Chávez, the circumstances were embedded in a history of elite Venezuelans who were capitalizing off the country's rich and plentiful oil resources. Additionally, the Real was the failed coup that Chávez waged against former President Carlos Andres Perez, which was incited by a massacre that took place three years earlier, the event that galvanized a collective of individuals to start supporting Chávez.

The paratrooper (Chávez) and his allies were enraged by Perez's orders to troops to mow down hundreds of people in the wake of food riots triggered by IMF-endorsed economic 'shock package.' It ended with one of the largest massacres in modern Latin American history, rivaling Tiananmen Square for the number of dead¹⁴.

Venezuelans found themselves desiring the ousting of Perez and supporting Chávez's possible rule. The circumstances turned to Chávez' presidency where he was responsible for implementing new socialist policies: In his first year as president, Venezuelans witnessed a rewriting of the constitution, policies in literacy and education, the supporting of food distribution and markets by subsidies from oil revenues, the distribution of land to many Venezuelans, and mostly by taking control of the oil corporation PDVSA so that the oil revenues could be redistributed to the poor of Venezuela through sustainable food production¹⁵. However, there is the other aspect of this Real: the portrayal of Chávez as a socialist totalitarian who was not working for the people, but still carrying on the oppressive policies of his predecessors. Venezuela's current economic and political circumstance gives weight to those who wish to fulfill this narrative of Chávez's presidency as having a negative

¹³ ID., *How to Read Lacan*, W.W. Norton, London - New York 2006, p. 15.

¹⁴ B. JONES, *Hugo! The Hugo Chávez Story from Mud Hut to Perpetual Revolution*, Steerforth Press, Hanover (NH) 2007, p. 207.

¹⁵ Cfr. *Ibid.*, p. 256.

impact on the country. The most damning critique of Chávez's rule was about his managerial competence:

After a decade of record oil revenues totaling around a trillion dollars, an unprecedented bounty, Venezuela is falling apart: roads crumbling, bridges falling, refineries exploding. A wheezing power grid produces regular black-outs. Public hospitals are dank, prisons filthy and barbaric. Murder and kidnapping rates have soared, imposing a de facto curfew in many cities. The currency was recently devalued for the fifth time in a decade. Many young professionals have emigrated. The economy is warping from subsidies and controls¹⁶.

Despite this, many Venezuelans revere Chávez and their belief in him as a symbol is substantiated by another symbolic belief that plays a crucial role in their support of him: they believe his detractors resent Chávez for having given power to the poor. Meanwhile, his detractors downplayed the Venezuelan support of Chávez by claiming that Venezuelans do not understand what he has done to the country. They claim Venezuelans are false in the belief that he was the embodiment of *Bolívarismo*. We should ask who is right in this matter. The answer is both. Chávez championed *Bolívarismo*, but the problem is that *Bolívarismo*, while effective in symbolically unifying Venezuelans, has been ineffective in the Real. This directs us to a general problem that the Lacanian triad proposes, an issue that Žižek highlights with interpassivity: the Symbol, instantiated by the Imaginary within the Real cannot successfully deal with the Real. This failure sets the stage for interpassivity because the breakdown leaves the individual with no choice but to live as if acting through the object of desire, in this case the accepted embodiment of *Bolívarismo*, Chavez. Žižek writes in *The Sublime Object of Ideology* that

what we call “social reality” is in the last resort an ethical construction; it is supported by a certain *as if* (we act *as if* we believe in the almightiness of

¹⁶ CARROLL, *Hugo Chávez: Poor Boy* cit. (note 161).

bureaucracy, as *if* the President incarnates the Will of the People, as *if* the Party expresses the objective interest of the working class...) ¹⁷.

What if Venezuelans simply acted as if Chavez had a big heart, as if he would summon the spirit of Bolívar to bring Venezuela back to Venezuelans? With such an “as if”, the interpassive relationship had a foothold, the symbolic could not be seen as a symbol but became intertwined in the social reality of Venezuelans.

Žižek applies this interpassive analysis to intellectuals as well. In his view, intellectuals are supposed to have an advantage in understanding these matters because they are typically viewed as having an unbiased vantage point from which to understand this tripartite dynamic involving Chávez. The intellectual view of Hugo Chávez is important for two reasons: 1) to see how interpassivity manifests through a theologico-political act between the people and Chávez; and 2) to see how the role of interpassivity between the intellectual and the subject at hand appears to be a type of intellectual distancing.

In *Living in the End Times*, Žižek briefly discusses Chávez asserting the theologico-political and taking on the role of a symbolic hero. Theologico-political is defined as being the suspension of the ethico-legal, where ethics in the form liberalism meets the legal in the form of jurisprudence. For example, the ethico is comprised of issues such as abortion; the discussion turns to the legal when discussing the topic in terms of rights. This comprehension of reality hides issues. It prevents fidelity to a cause and instead makes the issues into a bureaucratic enterprise. The theologico-political asserts that theology is the basis for politics and that politics is the basis for theology; the theologico-political creates each of its poles and has the potential to act as a chasm between the ethico-legal by suspending it and getting individuals closer to the Real. The inclusion of theology in a discussion about Chávez may seem odd, but Žižek abstracts away from its religious associations to see what the

¹⁷ S. ŽIŽEK, *The Sublime Object of Ideology*, Verso, London - New York 2008, p. 34.

theologico-political is on a structural level. For instance, in Christianity there is the collective that believes in the holy spirit (one part of the Christian Trinity). Žižek says that when examining Christianity «it is a fetishistic mistake to search for the material support of this form (the resurrected Christ) – the Holy Ghost is the very collective of believers, what they search for outside is already here in the guise of the love that binds them»¹⁸. Crucial to the idea of the holy spirit is the collective belief in the holy spirit: the metaphysical existence of such a spirit isn't the point as much as it is an obstacle from seeing what the real significance of the collective belief entails.

Structurally, belief and a collective of people is all that is required for the use of the theologico-political. The imaginary could be anything from Christ to Chávez, but the symbol of what they stand for and the belief in it is all that is important. Žižek writes that «far from signaling the corruption of a revolutionary process, the celebration of the leader's name is immanent to that process»¹⁹. Like the idea of the Holy Ghost, the collective support for the name, the symbol, is what gives force to the imaginary that name is instantiated by. Therefore, Chávez, coming into the national stage as a leader of a failed coup, was able to galvanize support for his cause: he simply embodied a revolutionary cause that a collective could support and wanted to support. He suspended the ethico-legal twice. The first suspension came when he tried to lead a coup and failed, wherein his symbol grew. The second suspension came when he won the election through a democratic election in Venezuela. The theologico-political remained. Žižek writes:

It is in these terms that one should read the “eccentric” fact that Hugo Chávez first tried to gain power by a military coup – only after the coup failed (and the anniversary of this attempt is today not hushed up but celebrated as a holiday in Venezuela) did he submit to elections as a second-best choice, and won. Thus in contrast to the standard scenario of the ambitious

¹⁸ ID., *Living in the End Times*, Verso, London - New York 2011, p. 118.

¹⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 128.

politician who, after losing the democratic election, tries to grab power through a coup, for Chávez, elections were a substitute for the coup²⁰.

Chávez put a face to the symbol of *Bolivarismo* and his supporters aligned with him and, what is more telling of this phase of the theologico-political in Venezuela, is that over the years of his presidency, the symbolic name slightly adjusted to the imaginary, where the imaginary of Chávez could now go by two symbolic references: the old symbol of *Bolivarismo* and the new symbol of *Chavismo*.

From the intellectual view, the powerful actors of theologico-political acts (leaders) set the stage for interpassivity, yet intellectuals are able create even more distance between themselves and these leaders. Based on Žižek's analysis of Vaclav Havel's *The Power of the Powerless*, we have another way of understanding Chávez that would help us identify how such a separation could happen with the general masses. After Chávez became president, the ruling ideology in Venezuela turned toward socialism, even if in practice it was not achieved. This makes Bolívar such a central figure to this country because in a populace that generally seeks for reform from the masses, an ideology that proposes to bring reform and power to the masses can find a hospitable environment to be accepted. One can have a belief that Chávez' socialist rule was right or that it was wrong. A committed belief to either will give rise to shared guilt. However, there are those who may try to avoid it. Žižek says of Havel that his «notion of an authentic 'living in truth' involves no metaphysics of truth or authenticity: it simply designates the act of suspending one's participation in the game, breaking out of the vicious cycle of 'objective guilt'»²¹. The question involves who exactly has cut themselves off from the vicious cycle of this guilt. It does not appear to be Chávez supporters or his detractors. Perhaps intellectuals have removed themselves from a situation in which the detraction of this socialist ideology would play into the hands of the ruling socialist regime. In critiquing the

²⁰ *Ibidem*.

²¹ ID., *Did Somebody Say Totalitarianism?* cit., p. 91.

Frankfurt School, Žižek says they were silent about Stalinism. This silence could mean two things: this first thing is it could have been the case that they did not want to be cornered and have their true allegiance to Western liberal democracy exposed. This exposure would play into Socialism by showing how the liberal elite was ensconced within a Western understanding of the government they purported to critique in their writings. Žižek says that «openly acknowledging this solidarity would deprive them of their ‘radical’ aura»²². The second thing is that by showing too much allegiance with socialist ideology, intellectuals risked betraying these Western liberal commitments. Thus, the intellectual attempts to avoid guilt by taking a peripheral stance outside of the dialogue between the detractors and the supporters of Chávez. Through this guilt avoidance, the intellectual passively interacts by letting the distance, and the way one speaks through such intellectual distance, *be* the interaction.

Though one may try to use distance, distance sets up its own interpassive grammar that only highlights how we all succumb to letting something else take over for us. Using VCRs as an example, Žižek simplifies interpassivity as the act of preventing action by letting some other thing act for the individual. They avoid the responsibility to act because there is something else doing the job for them. The thought of having a movie collection for a VCR allows the individual to be entertained by the idea that the VCR is in possession of what the person would be entertained by; thus, the object contains the source of joy while the individual no longer has the responsibility to himself of enjoying his movie collection; he is satisfied that the joy of it resides somewhere without his having to do anything²³. Then there is the obsessive neurotic person who keeps himself busy so that he can refrain from releasing his neurosis in the very act he wants to perform. These busy tactics are what Žižek calls false activity. It occurs «when people do not only act in order to change something, they can also act in order to prevent something from

²² *Ibid.*, p. 93.

²³ Cfr. ID., *How to Read Lacan* cit., p. 24.

happening so that nothing will change»²⁴. The academic gives in to these false activities by engaging in debates that practically go nowhere, but it keeps them busy. It allows them to say that they are doing something significant without doing anything significant; for Žižek, the second sense of significance would be the confrontation with the Real, qua Impossible. However, there is a way to face the Real: Žižek says this is done by withdrawing into passivity and doing nothing. For the neurotic this would mean he stops talking and he allows the silence with his analyst to foment. This means that academics must also stop talking and, rather, confront the conflict between what they are as imaginaries (instead of seeing what they are supposed to symbolically achieve in the academic game) and the circumstances of the Real. Žižek says this would «change the coordinates of the scene»²⁵. For Žižek, isolating the true activity into this mode of passivity helps distinguish the true from the false activity. We can also apply this analysis to the supporters and critics of Chávez. If not experiencing this collective guilt, then they are able to involve themselves in activities that prevent them from changing the coordinates of the scene. For the supporters (often called *Chávistas*) the break from the cycle of interpassivity would mean they could confront this collective guilt of knowing that while Chávez was being true to Bolívar's legacy, Bolívar's legacy wasn't true to their actual circumstances. It would be a confrontation with the Real as fraudulent.

Viewed as the fraudulent Real, Chávez would now have to be understood as a man who possibly had the best interests of the people in mind but had trouble successfully combining the symbolic order of Bolívar's legacy with the new troubles of the day. For Žižek, this is what it means to change the coordinates of the scene and to have fidelity to the Real²⁶. This is what allows people to confront the glaring problem of the Real, which is that «the Real is the internal stumbling block on account of which the symbolic system can never 'become itself,' achieve its self-

²⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 26.

²⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 27.

²⁶ Cfr. ID., *The Plague of Fantasies*, Verso, London - New York 1997, p. 278.

identity»²⁷. The same stumbling holds for Chávez' critics: Chávez was popular because Venezuelans have a committed belief (through inter-passivity) in their own freedom and they have the ability to communally participate in the advancement of their country.

Chávez viewed himself as a martyr for the Venezuelan people. He knew that his appearance, upbringing, and education, placed him a peculiar position to help the country. His supporters reveled in his personal history: «To the millions of poor people languishing in Venezuela's barrios and to a growing number of supporters around the world, he is El Comandante – the man who is leading Venezuela out of its bleak abyss»²⁸. When coming into power during his first term, he followed Tony Blair's concept of the "Third Way" which would place Venezuela between neoliberal capitalist and socialist policies. This way would involve massive policy changes involving the oil-dependent economic infrastructure of Venezuela, but then it would also be brought about by Venezuelans. In response to this permitted surge of power for the Venezuelan people, a coup against Chávez arose in April 2002. He was captured and imprisoned, only later to be retrieved by his loyalists in a counter assault to the coup. Reflecting on the coup, Chávez said:

The government, empowered by the National Assembly, wrote, as you know, 49 laws. Among them are: the land law, the bank law, the micro-finance law, the fishing law, the hydrocarbon law, laws that affect the historic interests of the oligarchy, of the ruling classes. When these classes saw that we had decided to deepen the process, and that we were about to transform the socioeconomic structure, they began to work toward their failed April 11 coup²⁹.

²⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 279.

²⁸ JONES, *Hugo! The Hugo Chávez Story*, cit., p. 497.

²⁹ M. PABIAN, *Venezuela: From Third Way to Socialist Revolution*. (Direct Action, November 2008); cfr. website http://directaction.org.au/issue4/venezuela_from_third_way_to_socialist_revolution (accessed on April 14, 2013).

Chávez had to respond to this “Third Away” approach by increasing his executive powers while still appearing to give Venezuelans some level of control of economic production. He knew, as Bolívar knew and current President Maduro is now finding out, that he originally offered too much control to the masses. Here we have Chávez admitting a symbolic position and knowing the effect it would have on Venezuelans. He understood they identified themselves with him and that his place in the national spotlight meant they had a voice on such a stage. We already understand that his supporters, critics, and the intellectuals all have a capacity to break from interpassivity to see Chávez’ in the Real; however, would it have been possible for Chávez to take the ‘true activity’ position regarding himself? Answering yes to this question supposes that Chávez might have suffered from regarding himself interpassively and that he might have kept himself in a cycle of false activity to ward off something that he could not confront as president. He would be his own Other in this sense, diverting away from himself to take on a new stance about himself.

I do not think this happened with Chávez. Rather, I hold, with Žižek, that while Chávez saw himself as a martyr, it was in an unusual sense. He saw himself as someone who had to do what was necessary; thus, he exhibited fidelity to the Real. Chávez viewed himself as a hero of the people. Žižek says of heroes that a «true hero is the one makes the necessary compromise, knowing that in a subsequent development this compromise will be denounced as treason and he personally will be liquidated – *this* is the highest service one can render to the Party»³⁰. Perhaps Chávez realized this after his policies of the “Third Way” led to the coup of 2002 and perhaps this is why he felt it was naïve for him to have implemented them. He said this much after the coup: «I naively took as a reference point Tony Blair’s proposal for a ‘third way’ between capitalism and socialism – capitalism with a human face»³¹. This helps explain another phenomenon regarding how people held Chávez as both

³⁰ ŽIŽEK, *Did Somebody Say Totalitarianism?*, cit., p. 99.

³¹ PABIAN, *Venezuela: From Third Way to Socialist Revolution*, cit.

a negative and positive phenomenon: the hero is someone who appears to be a traitor to his own cause and a liberator of his people. Without painting a romantic picture of Chávez, we could say that he was able to deal with the Impossible in a much more dynamic way than his critics or supporters. He couldn't be interpassive even though everyone else took that position. Ironically, he took the interactive approach by saying anything he wanted and acting in whatever way he felt. This was not interpassive, in which the issue was skirted to repress something dying to come out, as we saw with the obsessive neurotic. Rather, Chávez displayed interactivity where nothing was repressed and everything was confronted, an approach that incurred both failure and success for his country.

In this paper I hope to have explained how Hugo Chávez's symbolic stature arose from his use of *Bolívarismo* and from the need of Venezuelans to collectively believe in the continued existence of a revolutionary symbol. By examining interpassivity's role in the Lacanian triad, as elucidated by Žižek, I have shown that Chávez was the only individual to confront the Real as a problematic and that his supporters, critics, and intellectual spectators remained in an interpassive position in which they were unable to take the first step into seeing how Chávez's legacy was a consequence of his being the imaginary instantiation of the symbol of *Bolívarismo*. I have also explained how Chávez, being the sole confronter of this Real problematic, was able to use this knowledge of his symbolic meaning to the collective by asserting the theologico-political, wherein he showed that he could be a martyr for his people by suspending the ethico-legal strictures that constitute their shared reality. He was able to avoid a vicious cycle of guilt and encounter the Real, becoming an ambiguous hero: simultaneously viewed by some as a big-hearted revolutionary who gave Venezuela back to the poor and, to others, a detriment to the Latin American revolution inspired by Bolívar so long ago.